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**STUDY OF THE RELATIONS BETWEEN QUASI-HARMONIC COMPONENTS
 OF SPEECH SIGNALS IN THE CHINESE LANGUAGE**

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Processing of speech signals commonly involves their harmonic model as the aggregate oscillations at the pitch and overtones. The voiced sounds in the Chinese language feature lexically loaded variations in the pitch. When syllables with common vowels are pronounced, the nature of the pitch variations is used as a semantic distinguisher for their recognition. With reference to the sounds of this type our paper presents the analysis results describing the phase couplings between oscillations of the pitch and overtones. The study conducted proves that the analysis of this kind can be applied to improve the segmentation reliability of voiced speech segments and detection integrity of tiny displacements in the positions of articulators. The paper also presents the data of computer processing the speech signal phonograms made with the Chinese native speakers.

Introduction

The alternatives to reveal and use inter-component relations in the harmonic model of the voiced speech sounds in the Russian language in order to recognize components of speech signals and distinguish the speakers were discussed by the authors in a series of their papers (ref. for instance [1, 2]). Today this field of research is steel deemed very topical.

In what follows the authors dwell on the estimate of this kind of interconnections with reference to the sounds of the Chinese language.

Processing algorithm

Figure 1 illustrates the flow-chart of the algorithm used to extract the oscillations of the pitch and overtones of the voiced speech sounds and to evaluate their phase relationships.

Fig. 1. Flow-chart of the algorithm

It can be seen from Figure 1 that the signal processing procedure can be divided into several comparatively independent stages:

- calculation of short-period pitch estimates;
- calculation of instantaneous values of the pitch harmonic phases;
- calculation of the phase functions in question.

In order to calculate the short-period pitch estimates it appeared reasonable to use RAPT algorithm [3], that has proved to be highly efficient both for clear and noisy speech. The sketchy diagram of the RAPT algorithm is explicitly described by the pitch estimate block in Figure 1.

Calculation of the harmonic full-phase instantaneous values $\Phi_n(t)$ involves filtration of each n -th harmonic $h_n(t)$ of the pitch from the original signal $x(t)$ with a tunable bandpass filter at the speech-signal quasi-stationary interval. It was established through preliminary experiments that the signal quasi-stationary interval in the signals under study was approximately 40 μ s.

Hilbert transformation was applied to generate an analytic signal of the n -th harmonic $z_n(t)$. The argument of the analytic signal $\varphi_n(t)$ is the basic value of the full phase. In order to exclude over-period laps of the phase functions under study (for instance, the phase quasi-invariant) it is strongly recommended to manipulate with full phases $\Phi_n(t)$ of the pitch harmonics only. The harmonic full phases can be obtained by adding a non-negative number divisible by 2π to each of their instantaneous principal value. The need to do so is determined by the below considerations.

For the values, such as the sampling frequency F_s , the short-period pitch estimate $F_0(t)$, the half bandwidth of the filters F_b , used for the pitch harmonic selection, the finite difference $\Delta\Phi_n(t)$ of the full phase instantaneous filter for the n -th pitch harmonic must remain within the limits of

$$\Delta\Phi_n(t) = \Phi_n(t) - \Phi_n(t-1) \in [F_0(t) - F_b, F_0(t) + F_b] \cdot \frac{2\pi n}{F_s}. \quad (1)$$

An approximate estimate of the n -th harmonic full phase can be expressed through the formula

$$\Phi'_n(t) = n \int_0^t F_0(t) dt.$$

Based on the above the following algorithm has been generated to calculate the instantaneous values of the full phase.

1. Initially the full phase values for each n -th harmonic are accepted equal to the principal values: $\Phi_n(t) = \varphi_n(t)$.
2. Then for each point of reference $t = \overline{0, T}$ the following operations are repeated in sequence.
 - If the finite difference $\Delta\Phi_n(t)$ lies within the limits determined by expression (1), the full phase estimates are slightly adjusted

$$\Phi'_n(t') = \Phi'_n(t') - \Phi'_n(t) + \Phi_n(t) \text{ for } t' = \overline{t, T}.$$

– Otherwise

$$\Phi_n(t') = \Phi_n(t') + 2\pi \left\| \frac{\Phi'_n(t') - \Phi_n(t)}{2\pi} \right\|, \text{ for } t' = \overline{t, T},$$

where $\| \|$ mean rounding to the closest integer.

Experimental study of the phase quasi-invariant properties

It was established through preliminary experiments that the phase quasi-invariant allows sufficiently accurate tracking of the transition processes in cases of minor variations in the articulation. First of all, in order to figure out whether the phase analysis can be applied for speech segmentation, the authors performed the phrasal analysis for /i y e a o u/, pronounced by a Russian native speaker, male, having his average pitch at 125 Hz. This analysis result is shown in Figure 2.1. To prevent the recording circuit phase response ripple from influencing the analysis results the phrase was deliberately pronounced with approximately constant pitch value. The sequence of phonemes in the phrase /i y e a o u/ was selected so that to ensure minimal variations in the articulation when in transition from sound to sound.

Further study of the phase analysis capabilities to be used for speech segmentation was performed with the recorded speech in Chinese.

Figure 2.2 illustrates an example of the analysis of words /dai4 ya4 ye1 ya4 yu2 yue4/, representing the beginning of the following sentence 代亚耶亚鱼跃扑救也未能阻止这个进球 /dai4 ya4 ye1 ya4 yu2 yue4 pu1 jiu4 ye3

wei4 neng2 zu3 zhi3 zhe4 ge4 jin4 qiu2/, pronounced by a female speaker with her pitch varying from 150 to 360 Hz.

Fig. 2.1. Analysis of the phrase /i y e a o u/

Fig. 2.2. Analysis of the phrase /dai4 ya4 ye1 ya4 yu2 yue4/

Below is the legends for Figures 2.1 and 2.2:

- a) oscilloscope pattern of the signal;
- b) narrow-band spectral pattern, resulted from the Fourier Transform of the 40μs frame at a 2.5 μs step;
- c) spectral pattern of the linear prediction, calculated as the gain response of the 12-order prediction filter with 40μs frames at a 2.5 μs step;
- d) phase quasi-invariant $\Psi_1^{2,3}(t) = \Phi_1(t) + \Phi_3(t) - 2 \cdot \Phi_2(t)$;
- e) averaged in frequency with the analysis interval $\tau = 0.040ms$ time derivative of the linear prediction spectral pattern

$$\Xi(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \ln \frac{P(\omega, t)}{P(\omega, t - \tau)} d\omega,$$

where $\omega = 2\pi f / F_s$ is the normalized frequency f ; $P(\omega, t)$ stands for the power spectral density of the linear prediction spectral pattern. This characteristic is similar to a known distance estimate [4]

$$\log \text{ spectral distance } d(P, P')^p = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} |\ln P(\omega) - \ln P'(\omega)| d\omega.$$

The only difference is that the function *log spectral distance* is nonnegative, and $\Xi(t)$ can take both positive (for the sections with increased signal component power), and negative (for the sections with reduced signal component power) values.

e) logarithm of the ratio of Itakura-Saito distances between the spectral power density frames: $IS_2(t) = \ln \left[\frac{\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} (G(\omega, t) - \ln G(\omega, t) - 1) d\omega}{\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} (G^{-1}(\omega, t) + \ln G(\omega, t) - 1) d\omega} \right]$, where $G(\omega, t) = \frac{P(\omega, t)}{P(\omega, t - \tau)}$.

The function $IS_2(t)$ is the variant of the COSH-function, where the sum of the Itakura-Saito distances is replaced with the difference in order to achieve its similarity with the linear prediction spectral pattern derivative.

The Figures presented reflect on of the most complicated problems one faces in speech segmentation, namely distinguishing several voiced sounds in a row.

It is obvious from Figure 2.1 that using either the oscilloscope or spectral pattern, either the linear prediction spectral pattern derivative or the COSH-function directly for segmentation is rather complicated, whereas in the phase quasi-invariant function the quasi-stationary and transition areas are explicitly manifested. The auditory analysis proved the following are the boundaries of the sounds: sound /i/ – [0.1, 0.5] s., sound /y/ – [0.7, 1.0] s., sound /e/ – [1.2, 1.45] s., sound /a/ – [1.65, 2.0] s., sound /u/ – [2.6, 3.0] s. It was impossible to clearly define the boundaries of the sound /o/ in view of a considerable flatness of the transition between the sounds /a o u/.

It is evident from the example of the phrasal analysis for /dai4 ya4 ye1 ya4 yu2 yue4/, given in Figure 2.2, that preliminary segmentation of this phrase into sounds can succeed with only the linear prediction spectral pattern derivative and the function $IS_2(t)$. In the meantime, minor variations in the positions of articulators can be more effectively detected with the phase quasi-invariant analysis applied. For instance, it is much more efficient to use the phase quasi-invariant analysis in order to define the boundaries of the sound /j/ being [1.1, 1.171], rather than the functions $\Xi(t)$ and $IS_2(t)$.

The experiments conducted have shown that distinguishing tonal sounds in a continuous Chinese speech with the pitch variation profile only, as offered in the Patent [5], is very difficult. It can be efficient solely in case of isolates voiced tonal sounds. In the continuous Chinese speech there is a considerable mutual influence of adjacent sounds on each other. Therefore, inter-component phase analysis of harmonic components in the speech signal should be deemed of a huge practical interest for segmentation of adjacent voiced sounds.

Conclusions

Computer phase quasi-invariant analysis of oscillations at the pitch and at two of its closest overtones was used to study inter-component relations between the harmonics of tonal speech signals in Chinese. There is a dialogue software tool developed that automates such kind of signal processing. The analysis tool developed is a nice supplement to the well-known approaches of context-independent speech segmentation, enabling to improve the efficiency of distinguishing voiced speech sections and detect minor variations in articulation. Among the disadvantages of the tool its noise sensitivity and greater computational complexity should be mentioned in comparison with the procedures that use spectral derivative or COSH-function.

It is worth mentioning that in addition to the considered phase functions such as phase invariant and phase quasi-invariant, other inter-component characteristics of the speech signal might also be of considerable interest. Speech signal processing with tracking modes of the pitch frequency estimate used requires additional study.

The approaches and tools for inter-component signal processing developed and studied are applicable not only for speech signals, but also, for instance, for acoustic noises and vibrations of mechanisms and machinery.

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